

INTEGRATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL STANDARDS INTO AMERICAN COMPANIES: ANALYSIS OF METHODS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

This article explores the integration of environmental standards into American companies, focusing on the analysis of various methods and practical solutions. It examines traditional compliance approaches and innovative technological methods, such as Artificial Intelligence, Big Data analytics, and Internet of Things, to enhance environmental performance. The study provides case analyses of Walmart, Intel, and Procter & Gamble, showcasing their strategies and successes in incorporating these standards. These examples highlight significant improvements in sustainability, resource efficiency, and corporate responsibility, underscoring the importance of combining regulatory compliance with advanced technological solutions for comprehensive environmental integration.

Keywords: *environmental standards, sustainability, corporate responsibility, Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, IoT, American companies.*

Introduction

The integration of environmental standards into corporate practices has become increasingly critical in the context of global sustainability efforts. In the USA, businesses are facing growing pressure from regulatory bodies, consumers, and stakeholders to adopt environmentally responsible practices. This trend is driven by heightened awareness of environmental issues such as climate change, pollution, and resource depletion, which necessitate a more sustainable approach to business operations.

Environmental standards in the USA encompass a wide range of regulations and guidelines designed to mitigate the impact of industrial activities on the natural environment. These include federal laws such as the Clean Air Act, the Clean Water Act, and the Resource Conservation and Recovery Act, alongside numerous state-level regulations. Compliance with these standards not only ensures legal adherence but also enhances corporate reputation, fosters innovation, and can lead to significant economic benefits through improved efficiency and resource management.

Incorporating environmental standards into business operations requires a multifaceted approach that blends traditional methods with innovative technological solutions. Traditional methods often involve policy adherence, regulatory compliance, and the adoption of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives. However, emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data analytics, and the Internet of Things (IoT) offer new avenues for enhancing environmental performance and achieving sustainability goals. The objective of this article is to analyze the various methods and practical solutions for integrating environmental standards within American companies, with a particular emphasis on the role of advanced technologies.

Main part. Regulatory framework

The USA has a comprehensive framework of environmental regulations designed to protect natural resources, public health, and the environment. This framework is based on several federal laws and regulations that set standards for air quality, water quality, waste management, and chemical safety, including the Clean Air Act (CAA), the Clean Water Act (CWA), and the Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA).

The Clean Air Act regulates air emissions from various sources to ensure air quality meets health-based standards. The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) implements the CAA, setting National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) for pollutants harmful to public health and the environment [1]. Businesses must obtain emission permits, adhere to standards, and monitor and report pollutant levels.

The Clean Water Act regulates discharges of pollutants into surface waters to maintain water integrity [2]. The CWA prohibits discharging pollutants into navigable waters without a permit. The National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) program regulates sources discharging pollutants into USA waters, requiring companies to monitor discharges, comply with effluent limits, and report to the EPA.

The Resource Conservation and Recovery Act governs the disposal of solid and hazardous waste, establishing a system for hazardous waste management [3]. Businesses must comply with guidelines on waste identification, storage, transportation, treatment, and disposal, promoting resource recovery and conservation.

Recent trends emphasize integrating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) criteria and sustainable development principles into corporate strategies. ESG criteria are increasingly used by investors to evaluate the sustainability and ethical impact of companies. This trend is supported by documents like the USA Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) proposal for mandatory climate risk disclosures [4].

The USA has committed to international agreements like the Paris Agreement, aiming to limit global warming, and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), providing a framework for sustainability by 2030. These commitments drive national policies to reduce environmental impact and promote sustainable practices. The USA Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) 2024-2027 Climate Adaptation Plan outlines strategies to enhance climate resilience across EPA programs, emphasizing financial assistance for climate-resilient investments, integrating adaptation into rulemaking, and increasing climate literacy.

The Long-Term Strategy of the USA, outlines pathways to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG)

emissions by 2050. It emphasizes investment in eliminating net global GHG emissions by mid-century, cov-

ering every sector from decarbonizing electricity to reducing non-CO₂ emissions and scaling up CO₂ removal (fig.1).

Figure 1. USA historic emissions and projected emissions under the 2050 goal for net-zero [5]

Government support programs assist organizations in complying with environmental standards and promoting sustainability. The Climate Pollution Reduction Grants (CPRG) program provides nearly \$5 billion annually to help entities develop and implement plans to reduce GHG emissions. For 2024, the EPA will offer up to \$100 million in grants to support GHG emissions reporting and reduction for construction materials and products [6].

Businesses must develop environmental management systems to comply with legal requirements, mitigate impacts, and improve performance, often involving regular audits, permits, emission and discharge limits, responsible waste management, and accurate records. Companies are encouraged to adopt best practices in environmental management and sustainability, leveraging technological innovations to enhance compliance and efficiency.

Integration strategies for environmental standards

The integration of environmental standards into American companies involves a combination of traditional and technological methods. Traditional methods primarily focus on policy and regulatory compliance, along with CSR initiatives. These approaches ensure companies meet legal requirements and contribute positively to societal goals. Technological methods leverage advanced tools like AI, Big Data analytics, and the IoT to enhance environmental monitoring, sustainability reporting, and energy management. Together, these methods provide a comprehensive framework for integrating environmental standards into business operations, promoting sustainability, and improving overall environmental performance (table 1).

Table 1.

Methods of integration for environmental standards [7, 8]

Method	Description	Advantages	Challenges
Traditional methods			
Policy and regulatory compliance	Ensures adherence to environmental laws and regulations, including obtaining necessary permits and reporting.	Legal compliance, risk mitigation, enhanced reputation	High cost of compliance, complex regulatory landscape
CSR initiatives	Voluntary actions taken by companies to go beyond compliance, such as sustainability programs and community engagement.	Improved stakeholder relations, positive public image	Requires significant investment, potential for greenwashing
Technological methods			
AI for environmental monitoring	Utilizes AI to analyze environmental data, predict trends, and detect anomalies in real-time.	Increased accuracy, proactive issue management	High initial investment, need for skilled personnel
Big Data and analytics for sustainability reporting	Employs Big Data techniques to collect, process, and report on sustainability metrics, improving transparency.	Enhanced decision-making, comprehensive reporting	Data privacy concerns, integration complexity
IoT in energy management	Integrates IoT devices to monitor and control energy usage, enhancing efficiency and reducing waste.	Real-time monitoring, operational efficiency	Cybersecurity risks, infrastructure requirements

From the author's perspective, integrating environmental standards into American companies requires a blend of traditional compliance methods and innovative technological solutions. By combining policy adherence, CSR initiatives, and advanced technologies such as AI, Big Data, and IoT, companies can effectively manage their environmental impact, promote sustainability, and align with global environmental goals.

Practical integration of methods in American companies

Integrating environmental standards involves implementing a variety of strategies that align with both regulatory requirements and sustainability goals. Companies across various sectors are adopting a mix of traditional and technological methods to enhance their environmental performance. These methods not only ensure compliance with environmental regulations but also drive innovation and improve corporate reputation.

Walmart, the world's largest retailer, has made significant strides in integrating environmental standards into its operations. Walmart's Project Gigaton aims to reduce one billion metric tons of GHG from its global supply chain by 2030. The company works closely with suppliers to improve their environmental practices, emphasizing policy compliance and CSR initiatives. Walmart also uses IoT technology to enhance energy management in its stores, optimizing lighting, refrigeration, and HVAC systems. The integration of

these technologies has led to substantial energy savings and a reduction in the company's overall carbon footprint.

Since the inception of Project Gigaton in 2017, more than 6,000 suppliers have joined the initiative. As of FY2023, Walmart and its suppliers have reported reducing or avoiding over 750 million metric tons of emissions [9]. This progress underscores the company's commitment to sustainability and its ability to drive significant environmental improvements through collaborative efforts with its supply chain partners.

Intel Corporation has integrated environmental standards through a combination of regulatory compliance, CSR initiatives, and advanced technologies. The company aims to achieve net positive water use and 100% renewable energy use by 2030. Intel employs AI to optimize its manufacturing processes, reducing energy consumption and minimizing waste. The company also uses IoT devices to monitor and control energy usage in its facilities, enhancing operational efficiency. Intel's sustainability reporting is enhanced by Big Data analytics, providing detailed insights into the company's environmental performance and progress towards its sustainability goals.

The company's efforts in sustainability are demonstrated through the reduction in actual GHG emissions and the substantial increase in avoided emissions over the years (fig. 2).

Figure 2: Actual and prevented Intel GHG emissions, million metric tons CO₂ [10]

Intel has made substantial investments to support its environmental goals. In 2023, the company allocated \$425 million from its Green Bond proceeds to projects focused on pollution prevention, water stewardship, energy efficiency, renewable energy, and waste management. Intel's net positive water goal was advanced through the conservation of approximately 10,2 billion gallons of water internally and the restoration of 3,1 billion gallons through community collaborations [10].

Intel's approach to integrating environmental standards through innovative technologies and comprehensive reporting not only ensures regulatory compliance but also positions the company as a leader in corporate sustainability. This integration of traditional methods and cutting-edge technologies helps Intel to achieve its ambitious environmental goals and set a benchmark for the industry.

Procter & Gamble (P&G) has been a pioneer in integrating modern practical solutions to achieve its environmental goals. One of the company's flagship initiatives is the Climate Transition Action Plan (CTAP), which outlines its commitment to achieving net zero

GHG emissions across its supply chain and operations by 2040. The plan prioritizes reducing emissions through innovative product design, operational efficiencies, and sustainable sourcing. P&G is also a leader in leveraging renewable energy, having achieved 97% renewable electricity usage globally as of 2021. This commitment is further bolstered by long-term partnerships to develop over 500 MW of new clean energy projects, sufficient to power approximately 125,000 USA homes annually [11].

To drive material innovation, P&G is focusing on increasing material efficiency, using bio-based materials, and developing technologies that reduce GHG emissions. For instance, the company is working with the Silicon Valley start-up Twelve to incorporate ingredients made from captured CO₂ into Tide products, aiming to create a fossil-free pathway for ingredient sourcing. P&G scientists have developed a technology that converts lactic acid into bio-based acrylic acid, which can be used in various everyday products. This innovation, licensed to Cargill, is expected to reduce GHG emissions by over 50% compared to traditional

petroleum-based equivalents [11]. P&G's focus on sustainable materials extends to its packaging, with initiatives such as the HolyGrail project, which uses digital watermarks to improve recycling efficiency. P&G is also harnessing advanced technologies such as AI and the IoT to enhance its environmental performance. The company employs AI to optimize its manufacturing processes, reducing waste and improving energy efficiency. AI-driven predictive maintenance systems are used to monitor equipment health, preventing breakdowns and minimizing downtime, which leads to reduced energy consumption and lower emissions. IoT sensors are deployed across P&G's facilities to monitor real-time energy usage, water consumption, and waste generation. This data-driven approach allows for precise control and optimization of resources, ensuring maximum efficiency and minimal environmental impact.

In addition to these measures, P&G uses Big Data analytics to enhance its sustainability reporting and track progress towards its environmental goals. By analyzing vast amounts of data collected from its operations, P&G can identify patterns and trends, make informed decisions, and implement targeted actions to further reduce its environmental footprint. This comprehensive use of AI, IoT, and Big Data analytics underscores P&G's commitment to leveraging technology for sustainable development.

In the USA, major companies are increasingly committed to transparency and accountability in their ESG practices, demonstrated through the annual publication of ESG reports [12]. These reports provide detailed insights into the companies' sustainability efforts, social impact, and governance practices, offering stakeholders a comprehensive view of their commitments and progress. The preparation and accuracy of these reports are significantly enhanced by advanced technological methods. Companies leverage AI for data analysis and predictive insights, Big Data analytics for comprehensive data aggregation and trend identification, and the IoT for real-time monitoring of environmental metrics. These technologies enable companies to efficiently track, report, and improve their ESG performance, ensuring that their operations align with global sustainability goals and regulatory requirements.

Conclusions

The integration of environmental standards into American companies requires a multifaceted approach that blends traditional compliance methods with innovative technological solutions. Traditional methods, such as adherence to regulatory frameworks and CSR initiatives, ensure legal compliance and enhance corporate reputation. However, these methods can be resource-intensive and complex. The adoption of advanced technologies, such as AI, Big Data analytics, and the IoT, significantly enhances environmental monitoring, sustainability reporting, and energy management. These technologies enable real-time data analysis, predictive modeling, and efficient resource management, thereby improving overall environmental performance and compliance.

Case studies of Walmart, Intel, and Procter & Gamble demonstrate the practical application of these methods. Walmart's Project Gigaton, Intel's net positive water and renewable energy initiatives, and Procter & Gamble's Climate Transition Action Plan highlight

the significant environmental benefits achieved through the integration of advanced technologies and traditional methods. These companies have successfully reduced their carbon footprints, improved resource efficiency, and enhanced their sustainability efforts, setting industry benchmarks for environmental responsibility. The findings underscore the importance of combining regulatory compliance with technological innovation to achieve effective environmental integration.

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